

POLICY BRIEF

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NEW START TREATY REVIEW: PAVING THE WAY TO STRATEGIC STABILITY IN THE 21ST CENTURY

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POLICY STATEMENT

Among the challenges faced in the 20th century, a nuclear war threat has caught the international community's attention. The containment of nuclear danger gained space on the superpowers' agenda, becoming a prominent theme in the cooperative processes between the United States of America (USA) and the Soviet Union (USSR), later, Russia. The abandonment of the ABM Treaty and doubts surrounding the New START Treaty, despite its five-year extension, would put the International System's strategic stability to the test. This pressure is even greater in the face of the development of new weapons technologies. This policy brief presents a brief overview of nuclear arms agreements and their future related to new strategic weapons.

BACKGROUND

Joint efforts to reduce and limit nuclear arsenals, after all, resulted in universal recognition of the concept of strategic stability, the fundamental pillar of which was laid down in the 1972 Anti-Ballistic Missile Treaty (ABM). Then, strategic stability emanates from a mutual renunciation of antiballistic missile defense systems, guaranteeing, on the other hand, reciprocal vulnerabilities to the nuclear states.

In the wake of the ABM Treaty, a series of international agreements were established aimed at controlling strategic armaments, including the Intermediate-Range Nuclear Forces Treaty (INF) and the Strategic Arms Reduction Treaty I, II and III (START I, II and III), subsequently, the New START Treaty. As a result, a nuclear non-proliferation regime was established, agreements to ban nuclear tests, eliminate chemical and biological weapons, and reduce conventional weapons. Such measures endeavored to institutionalize the relations between the superpowers around strategic armaments, aiming at removing the danger of a Nuclear Winter¹ (SAGAN, 1983).

As the 21st century begins, the debate on strategic stability is rekindled in two ways: i) technological development and ii) institutional abandonment. The first is postulated by technological advances in conventional high-precision weapon systems and Ballistic Missile Defense Systems. While the second refers to the abandonment of certain institutionalization processes of the limitation and reduction of nuclear weapons.

FINDINGS

Technological development has given pace for the institutionalization of strategic stability. Initially, the Nuclear Triad's consolidation (strategic bomber, ICBM, and SLBM) paved the way for the development of defensive technologies (ABM systems) that set the pace for strategic arms control and limitation negotiation agreements. Today, new strategic weapon systems (nuclear and conventional) operated by the USA and Russia are a fine line to the rupture of strategic stability.

On the part of the USA, reference is made to an offensive axis, covering the capabilities linked to the Prompt Global Strike (PGS) project, and to a defensive axis, which comprises National Missile Defense (NMD)¹. The first incorporates the existing nuclear arsenal of the "traditional triad," long-range conventional systems, and hypersonic speed weapons (Conventional Prompt Global Strike). They are comprised of new technologies projects in ballistic missiles (Conventional Strike Missile, Sea-Launched Intermediate-Range Ballistic Missile); hypersonic glider vehicles (Hypersonic Test Vehicle-2, Advanced Hypersonic Weapon); hypersonic cruise missiles (High-Speed Strike Weapon-HSSW; X-51A WaveRider); and hypersonic weapons to be commissioned on the strategic bombers B-52 (Hypersonic Conventional Strike Weapon; Tactical Boost Glide and the Air-Launched Rapid Responds Weapon)¹.

The defensive axis comprises the Ballistic Missile Defense System, an integrated defense architecture against ballistic missiles before they reach their final targets. Among its elements are sensor bodies and missile interception systems in its three phases of flight: ascent, mid-course (missiles RIM-161 SM-3, Aegis Ballistic Missile Defense), and terminal (THAAD, Patriot Advanced Capability PAC-3, and Aegis Ashore)¹. To make this system feasible, partly operational via NMD on American soil and via European Phased Adaptive Approach (EPAA) on European soil, Washington unilaterally broke with the ABM Treaty, removing the institutional hurdles that limited the system's development.

Regarding Russian systems, Moscow begins the development of several modernization projects and the development of new armaments to circumscribe and contain the United States' anti-missile defense capabilities to resume and guarantee strategic stability levels. Thus, they will operationalize new nuclear-powered cruise missile systems (Burevestnik), mobile laser weapon systems (Perevest), hypersonic air-to-ground ballistic missile (Kinzhal), nuclear-powered unmanned underwater vehicles (Poseidon), intercontinental ballistic missile missiles of unlimited range (Sarmat), and hypersonic glider vehicles subject to conventional and nuclear commissioning (Avangard). Also noteworthy are the new submarines of the Borei class and the cruise missile class Kalibr. They also take over the Soviet counter-value response system, Perimeter¹.

It is important to highlight that the modernization of Russian strategic forces is intended to maintain nuclear parity with the United States and preserve the country's retaliatory capacity, eroded by the USA's conventional precision ammunition systems (CPGS) and anti-missile defense systems (BMD).

Thus, institutional abandonment is linked to the technological development of new weapons systems and refers to the USA's unilateral withdrawal from treaties that institutionalize efforts to reduce nuclear weapons. Although its extension and the highlight to the ABM Treaty were signed, doubts remain about a subsequent agreement to the New START Treaty.

It should be noted that the ABM Treaty structures a concept that recognizes that only the maintenance of reciprocal vulnerabilities would be able to ensure nuclear balance since any claim of victory in a nuclear war is illusory.

In the end, it establishes the limiting of defensive systems, encouraging the limitation and reduction of strategic weapons. The United States denounced the ABM treaty in 2001 in favor of developing and implementing missile defense systems. From then on, the New START Treaty is seen as axial to the nuclear relations between the USA and Russia.

The New START was signed on April 8, 2010. Among the main provisions is the commitment of the parties to reduce their arsenals nuclear as not to exceed the number of 700 ICBMs, SLBMs, and heavy strategic bombers; 1,550 warheads deployed in the 700 systems mentioned above, and 800 vehicles (deployed and not deployed) launchers of ICBMs, SLBMs, and heavy bombers. The parties have the right to define how their strategic forces will be structured based on the above restrictions.

The Treaty also mentions the impact on the strategic stability of ICBMs and SLBMs in a non-nuclear configuration. In its preamble, it comprehensively addresses the issue from the statement that both nations are "aware of the impact of ICBMs and SLBMs armed with conventional warheads on strategic stability"¹. However, the Treaty does not present any restrictions to the parties for the provision of long-range precision attack capabilities. It is understood that any and all ballistic missiles of the intercontinental range, whether in terrestrial and marine vectors, will be included in the maximum count of 700 ICBMs, SLBMs, and heavy bombers in the disposal. In the same way that conventional warheads in these systems will be in the scope of 1,550 warheads (except for the percentage of nuclear warheads in heavy bombers). However, New START's Article V opens up space for implementing new strategic offensive weapons systems under the parties' right to raise questions before the Bilateral Consultative Commission. Unless the intended terminally guided ballistic missiles are entirely new technology, they will fall under the New START Treaty count. Boost-glide and hypersonic cruise missiles do not fall within the limitation.

The recent extension of New START for another five years gives strength to strategic stability¹(until February 4th, 2026). However, diplomatic efforts are urgent to ensure a follow-on agreement to achieve deeper mutual reductions in their stockpiles and cover new conventional strategic weapons under development and/or operation.

CONCLUSIONS

Given the above mentioned, it can be inferred that the break with the commitment to nuclear equity, caused by the abandonment of the ABM Treaty, may signal a new arms race. The proposition gains strength in the face of the growing distance between the signatory parties to the strategic stability agreements. This disjunction between the USA and Russia may be related to the operationalization of new weapons systems, directly impacting strategic stability. In addition to the extension of the New START Treaty, what we see today is a status of alarming corrosion of the political and military milieu whose escalation can, so soon, culminate in an exchange of nuclear artifacts. Therefore, it becomes relevant to reinstitutionalize a strategic relationship to eliminate the "incentives of a first nuclear attack."

SUGGESTIONS

In addition to extending the New START Treaty for another five years, the parties need to engage in diplomatic negotiations and efforts that will ultimately result in the signing of a new treaty, with the suggestion of incorporating themes such as:

1. the relationship (and definition) between offensive and strategic defensive weapons;
2. conventional strategic weapons (definition and capabilities);
3. the speed problem (hypersonic);
4. the MIRV warheads.

Although nuclear arsenals from other states were not mentioned in the policy brief and are not treated as a priority measure, it's important to keep in mind and articulate ways to bring China to the negotiating table. The risks associated with non-institutionalization should be better studied; however, the International System is subjected to witness a new arms spiral using the Cold War as an example. It is necessary to resume and maintain the institutionalization of relations between the USA and Russia and to limit, in a predictable horizon, the threat of a nuclear holocaust.

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